

Teachers' Adversity and Learners' Performance

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Abstract:

Addressing the interconnected issues of teachers' adversity and learners' performance requires a holistic approach involving teachers, school administrators, policymakers, and other stakeholders. In this context, this descriptive study examined the teachers' levels of adversity and learners' performance in a public secondary school in a medium-sized Division in Central Philippines during the School Year 2022-2023. It used a valid, reliable, self-made questionnaire to collect data from 69 teacher-respondents. Initial results showed that most teachers were older, female, married, and had longer lengths of service. Subsequent analysis showed teachers registering a high level of adversity and an outstanding level of learners' academic performance. No significant difference exists in the teachers' level of adversity in emotional, mental, and financial aspects when grouped according to demographics. Finally, no significant relationship exists between the levels of teachers' adversity and learners' performance. These findings call for the need to prioritize the well-being of teachers to have a positive ripple effect on the learners' educational experience.

Keywords: Education, teachers' adversity, learner's performance, Negros Occidental, Philippines

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Everybody faces adversity. This reality is not an exception for teachers. Teachers' various roles are rife with difficult social, mental, emotional, and professional, including financial challenges that can occasionally manifest as ravaging storms that threaten one's ability to continue working in the public education system. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has increased the difficulties teachers face in their personal and professional lives, necessitating a great deal of flexibility, imagination, and fortitude. Different countries worldwide have introduced various answers during the pandemic to continue the education process - the introduction of distance learning (Tria, 2020). Likewise, it can be extremely emotionally taxing for the teachers to adjust to new teaching methods, motivate students, and manage their behavior. This can result in compassion fatigue or secondary trauma (Day & Hong, 2016).

The predictable value that teachers must carry out over a set period can be summed up in one simple definition of a teacher's work performance (Asaloei et al. 2020). Likewise, given that many teachers need help to cover their basic daily expenses, it is not surprising that they are dissatisfied with their current financial situation (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014). Given the nature of the work that educators must do in the midst of a pandemic, it is critical to consider the adversity of teachers. From experiences, the researcher has also been exposed to stress and adversities, specifically in bridging learning gaps caused by disruptions. The researcher felt compelled to look into this subject in the context of public secondary schools despite the abundance of literature on teachers' adversity. The researcher also had a burning desire to help stressed-out and adversely affected teachers and develop a program to aid in these.

Current State of Knowledge

Teachers' Adversity. Adversity can be defined in a variety of ways, including minor day-to-day inconveniences. According to Canivel (2010), there are three types of adversity: societal, workplace, and individual. The economic sector faced numerous challenges during this difficult period, leaving most workers fighting for survival. Similarly, Pulsifer (2020) stated that according to Nordtveit (2016) the profession is at the core of protecting children, even though many teachers lack knowledge of pedagogic or psychosocial tools to deal with adversity or vulnerability. In addition, (Okorji & Epetuku, 2019) claim that the nature of the work that school leaders and teachers must perform

in the midst of a pandemic, is critical to consider their ability to overcome adversities and unprecedented challenges. Furthermore, Cardullo et al. (2021), assert that emergency remote instruction caught teachers off guard due to a lack of distance education expertise and computer literacy. Similarly, (Lagua, 2020). Also claims that the teachers shall receive training to help them provide better instruction in the face of the COVID-19 threat. Teachers, however, cannot simply ignore uncontrollable circumstances.

As a result, (Ketchell 2015) claims that a research report entitled "Too many teachers teaching outside their area of expertise," non-specialist teachers may be concerned about the negative effects their instruction may have on students' learning, such as lower achievement scores. They may also be concerned that they cannot present material relevant to daily life. In addition, Saleem et al. (2019) results of the study highlighted that teachers who are new and longer in service have a problem with the behavioral management of students as some teachers don't seem to be equipped to handle the issue, and the conventional classroom management techniques of those in longer in-service employ don't seem to be having the desired effect. On the other hand, Delmo et al. (2023) study on Financial Literacy and Financial Management Practices of Public-School Teachers revealed that nearly all working public school teachers have no other source of income, which may be because they don't have enough time to pursue other interests that could generate extra cash. Similarly, Carel and Pecajas's (2022) study showed that financial adversity based on the demographic profile of teachers, particularly their financial behavior, is not directly related to or has not affected their performance. At the same time, Koross's (2010) study found a correlation between students' performance and teachers' stress levels. Teachers working in underprivileged environments had the highest levels of stress among them. However, it conforms to Baraza's (2017) study, which concluded that stress levels among secondary school teachers had a weak negative influence on students' academic performance, and the influence was not significant.

Learners Performance. Brew et al. (2021) cited that many factors influence academic performance, including parents' educational levels and income, teachers' subject knowledge, truancy, textbook availability and accessibility, libraries, practical laboratories, meal provision, and many others. Similarly, student success is essential for higher education institutions because it is an important criterion for evaluating their quality (National Commission for Academic Accreditation (Amp, 2015). In addition, Arshad et al. (2015) study showed, students' high academic performance is because of the students' effort. If they want to improve their academic performance, then they will. On the contrary, Razak et al.'s (2019) study showed many factors influencing students' academic performance that may lose their motivation to study hard. Thus, Egalite's (2020) survey stated that family income directly impacts a child's education. Poverty directly affects academic achievement due to the lack of resources available for students' success.

In a study of Magulod's (2019) study showed that the majority of the students have high academic achievement. Perceptual learning styles, specifically auditory learning style, group learning style preference, kinesthetic learning style, and individual learning styles which is significant differences in their study habits were found when grouped according to their academic standing in high school, writing skills, and parents' education. On the one hand, the study by Badua et al. (2021) revealed that gender, age, average hours of sleep per day, and birth order do not affect academic performance. Furthermore, the dominant learning styles among respondents have no significant effect on their academic performance in science when the impact of some sociodemographic variables is statistically controlled and treated as a covariate. As a result, regardless of the student's dominant learning style, it has no bearing on their academic performance.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This research study is anchored on the Adaptation Model and Adversity authored by Dr. Roy (2008), in which people go through different adversities in life and are able to deal with them differently from other people. Despite the stressful situations like this pandemic that teachers and other sectors are experiencing, some of them can stand, strengthen, and overcome these adversities, yet others do not. The principle of human nature that upholds a shared sense of purpose in life is known as veritativity. The Roy adaptation model purposefully seeks knowledge that describes the coming together that is the opposite of adversity because adaptation is seen as the process and outcome where thinking and feeling persons, as individuals or in groups, use conscious awareness and choice to create human and environmental integration. This theory is anchored in this study as it seeks to explain challenging things like adversity, change, loss, and risk and how teachers will be able to adapt to these. This theory is best in determining the level of adversity of teachers. The present study also incorporated The Theory of Performance (ToP) by Elger (2007). By developing and connecting six fundamental concepts, the theory develops a framework that can be used to explain performance as well as performance enhancements (italicized). Performing means producing worthwhile results. A performer is a person or a group of people who collaborate to put on a performance. Your level of performance indicates your current stage of performance development. The current level of performance is influenced by six factors: context, level of knowledge, level of skills, level of identity, personal factors, and fixed factors. The theory proposes three axioms as effective performance improvements. They entail developing a performer's mindset, engaging in an environment, and practicing reflectively. Through the

concept of evaluating the organization's level of performance, ToP supports organizational learning. The theory of performance (ToP), which Elger thought was useful in various learning contexts, is obviously relevant and anchored to the present study. Once more, the theory describes specific elements of the research that give the investigation context and give the reader a foundation for understanding the performance level of learners.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the teachers' levels of adversity, and learners' performance in one of the public secondary schools in a medium-sized Division in Central Philippines during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following variables when grouped according to age, sex, civil Status, and , length of Service; the level of adversity of teachers according to the following areas when grouped according to emotional, mental, and financial; the level of learners' performance during the whole School Year 2022-2023; Is there a significant difference in the level of adversity of teachers when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; Is there a significant difference in the level of teacher's performance when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; and Is there a significant relationship between the level of adversity of teachers and the level of learners' performance.

Hypothesis

Based on the aforementioned problems, the following hypotheses are forwarded: There is no significant difference in the level of adversity of teachers when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; There is no significant relationship between the level of adversity of teachers and the level of learner's performance; and There is no significant relationship between the level of work-related stressors of teachers and their level of learner's performance.

Research Methodology:

Research Design

A descriptive research design was used in this study to determine the teachers' levels of adversity and work-related stressors in relation to learners' performance in one of the public secondary schools in a medium-sized Division in Central Philippines during the School Year 2022-2023. The descriptive research is a study of status and is widely used in education, epidemiology, nutrition and the behavioral sciences. The value is based on the premise that problems can be solved and practices can be improved through observation, description and analysis. The most common descriptive research method is the survey, which includes questionnaires, personal interviews, phone surveys, and normative surveys (Kowalczyk, 2018). This research design fits the purpose of the present study as it entails observation, analysis, and mainly a description of factors in the teachers' levels of adversity and work-related stressors about learners' performance.

Study Respondents

The study's respondents were 69 public secondary school teachers with advisory in one of the public secondary schools in a medium-sized Division in Central Philippines during the School Year 2022-2023. Since the total number of respondents is manageable, purposive sampling techniques were used. A purposive sample refers to a non-probability sample based on the characteristics of its population and the study's objective (Crossman, 2020).

Instruments

This study used a self-made questionnaire to gather all the data, mainly from teacher respondents. It contains the questionnaire proper on the level of adversity of teachers with items focused on the areas of Emotional, Mental and Financial. Each item was rated on a scale of 1 to 5, where 5 was interpreted as always, 4 as often, 3 as sometimes, 2 as rarely, and 1 as almost never.

Data Gathering Procedure

For the smoother conduct of the study, the researcher sought permission from the School Heads and the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) through the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) to undertake the study. Accordingly, a letter of request was sent to the school heads. Upon approval, the researcher scheduled the questionnaire's administration on a mutually convenient schedule for the respondents and the researcher. The researcher administered the questionnaires to the target respondents face to face, observing the safety health protocols such as wearing a mask, wearing face shields, and social distancing. All data gathered in this study were

treated with the utmost confidentiality. An orientation was done to present the objectives of the study and how to answer the survey questionnaire. Upon retrieval of the survey questionnaire, the data gathered was sent to the statistician for tabulation, application of the appropriate statistical tools in every problem, analysis, and presentation of the data in a tabular manner.

Procedures for Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

The respondents answered a research made questionnaire which underwent validity and reliability testing before its administration. The descriptive analytical scheme were employed to reveal the dynamics involved in the process. Frequency count, percentage, mean, Mann-Whitney U test, and Spearman Rho were used to treat the descriptive and inferential data.

To analyze the data and address the different objectives, the researchers have employed descriptive and comparative analytical schemes and adhered to the following statistical frequency count and percentage to determine the profile of respondents, Mann-Whitney U-Test to find out significant difference the respondent are group according to the variables as mentioned above. For the levels of technological difficulties, mean scores were interpreted as follows:

Range Score	Verbal Interpretation
4.50 - 5.00	Very High Level
3.50 - 4.49	High Level
2.50 - 3.49	Moderate Level
1.50 - 2.49	Low Level
1.00 - 1.49	Very Low Level

Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that no personal data compromising the respondents' identity was collected in adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, specifically on accessing the data both by the researcher and the analyst. The researcher was the only person with access to all data gathered. The respondents assured that no information that discloses their identity was released or published without their consent to the said disclosure, except when necessary to protect their rights and welfare. Likewise, all collected materials were appropriately disposed of by machine shredding or dissolved in water after the publication of the study. Furthermore, soft copies of the data were deleted with no chance of future retrieval.

Result and Discussions

This section presents, analyzes, and interpret the data gathered to carry out the results pertaining to the objective of the studies.

Table 1
Level of adversity of teachers in the area of emotional

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulty in...		
1. managing and controlling patience in teaching students	3.26	Moderate Level
2. expressing concerns to my co-teachers and school head.	3.15	Moderate Level
3. competitive and confrontational workplace.	3.13	Moderate Level
4. having space to discuss my emotions and issues	3.13	Moderate Level
5. managing conflicts between parents	3.07	Moderate Level
6. managing the behavior of students	4.46	High Level
7. responding to bullying situation	3.02	Moderate Level
Mean	3.32	Moderate Level

Table 1 result shows an overall mean score of 3.32, which is interpreted as a moderate level. Item no. 7 got the lowest mean score of 3.02, which states that "responding in a bullying situation" is interpreted as a moderate level. In contrast, Item no. 6 got the highest mean score of 4.46, which states that "managing behavior of students" is interpreted as a high level.

Table 2
Level of adversity of teachers in the area of mental

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulty in...		
1. accomplishing reports and other paper works on time	4.97	Very High Level
2. looking for resources available to help struggling students.	3.04	Moderate Level
3. learning ICT utilization in classes and personal use	4.00	High Level
4. hours spent on paperwork and insufficient time for vacation/leisure	4.00	High Level
5. seminars related to my ancillaries.	3.89	High Level
6. independently working with parents and other stakeholders to help resolve classroom/school issues.	3.98	High Level
7. the presence of excessive workload and hours of work	4.00	High Level
Mean	3.98	High Level

Table 2 result shows an overall mean score of 3.98, which is interpreted as a high level. Item no. 2 got the lowest mean score of 3.04, which states "looking for resources available to help struggling students," which is interpreted as a moderate level. In contrast, item no. 1 got the highest mean score of 4.97, which states that "accomplishing reports and other paperwork on time" is interpreted as a very high level.

Table 3
Level of adversity of teachers in the area of financial

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am having difficulty in...		
1. mounting teaching expenses in school	4.02	High Level
2. providing for the needs of my children and family.	3.97	High Level
3. huge debts and shark loan companies.	4.00	High Level
4. having a full command of my financial resources without hang-ups.	3.94	High Level
5. creating opportunities for myself to have an extra income after school hours.	4.82	Very High Level
6. managing ends meet from the last to the next salary day.	3.92	High Level
7. saving a little extra from the remuneration I receive.	3.97	High Level
Mean	4.09	High Level

Table 3 result shows an overall mean score of 4.09, interpreted as high. Item no. 6 got the lowest mean score of 3.92, which states "managing ends meet from the last to the next salary day," interpreted as a high level. In contrast, Item no. 5 got the highest mean score of 4.82, which states "creating opportunities for myself to have an extra income after school hours," interpreted as a very high level.

Table 4
Level of learners' academic performance during the School Year 2022 - 2023

Variable	Mean	Interpretation
Academic Performance	90.18	Outstanding

Table 4 shows the last year's GPA which measures a student's academic performance level. The table shows a mean score of 90.18, interpreted as outstanding. This means that the academic performance of the learners was excellent. Further, it means that effective teachers produce better-performing students.

Table 5
Level of adversity of teachers in the area of emotional when grouped according to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...				
1. managing and controlling patience in teaching students	3.28	Moderate Level	3.24	Moderate Level
2. expressing concerns to my co-teachers and school head.	3.18	Moderate Level	3.13	Moderate Level
3. competitive and confrontational workplace.	3.12	Moderate Level	3.13	Moderate Level
4. having space to discuss my emotions and issues	3.12	Moderate Level	3.13	Moderate Level
5. managing conflicts between parents	3.06	Moderate Level	3.08	Moderate Level
6. managing the behavior of students	4.46	High Level	4.45	High Level
7. responding to a bullying situation	3.03	Moderate Level	3.02	Moderate Level
Mean	3.32	Moderate Level	3.31	Moderate Level

Table 5 shows an overall mean score of 3.32 for the younger group and 3.31 for the older group, interpreted as moderate level. Item No. 7, which states "responding in a bullying situation," got the lowest mean score of 3.03 for the younger group and 3.02 for the older group, interpreted as a moderate level. On the other hand, item No. 6, which states "managing behavior of students," got the highest mean score of 4.46 for the younger group and 4.49 for the older group, which can be interpreted as a high level.

Table 6
Level of adversity of teachers in the area of emotional when grouped according to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...				
1. managing and controlling patience in teaching students	3.21	Moderate Level	3.28	Moderate Level
2. expressing concerns to my co-teachers and school head.	3.21	Moderate Level	3.13	Moderate Level
3. competitive and confrontational workplace.	3.13	Moderate Level	3.13	Moderate Level
4. having space to discuss my emotions and issues	3.04	Moderate Level	3.17	Moderate Level
5. managing conflicts between parents	3.04	Moderate Level	3.08	Moderate Level
6. managing the behavior of students	4.21	High Level	4.58	Very High Level
7. responding to a bullying situation	3.04	Moderate Level	3.02	Moderate Level
Mean	3.27	Moderate Level	3.34	Moderate Level

Table 6 shows an overall mean score of 3.27 for the male group and 3.34 for the female group, interpreted as a moderate level. Item Nos. 4, 5, and 7, which respectively state, "having space to discuss my emotions and issues", "managing conflicts between parents," and "responding in a bullying situation," got the lowest mean score of 3.04 for male group interpreted as moderate level while lowest score of female groups is 3.02, interpreted as moderate level also in item no. 7. On the other hand, Item No. 6 which states "managing behavior of students" got the highest mean score of 4.21 for male group interpreted as high level and 4.58 for female group, interpreted as very high level.

Table 7
Level of adversity of teachers in the area of emotional when grouped according to Civil Status

Items	Single		Married	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...				
1. managing and controlling patience in teaching students	3.31	Moderate Level	3.24	Moderate Level
2. expressing concerns to my co-teachers and school head.	3.31	Moderate Level	3.1	Moderate Level
3. competitive and confrontational workplace.	3.10	Moderate Level	3.14	Moderate Level
4. having space to discuss my emotions and issues	3.05	Moderate Level	3.16	Moderate Level
5. managing conflicts between parents	3.05	Moderate Level	3.08	Moderate Level
6. managing the behavior of students	4.36	High Level	4.5	Very High Level
7. responding to bullying situation	3.05	Moderate Level	3.02	Moderate Level
Mean	3.32	Moderate Level	3.32	Moderate Level

Table 7 shows an overall mean score of 3.32 for the single group and 3.32 for the married group, interpreted as moderate level. Item Nos. 4, 5, and 7, which respectively state "having space to discuss my emotions and issues", "managing conflicts between parents," and "responding in a bullying situation," got the lowest mean score of 3.05 for single group interpreted as moderate level while lowest score of married groups is 3.02, interpreted as moderate level also in item no. 7. On the other hand, Item No. 6 which states "managing behavior of students" got the highest mean score of 4.36 for single group interpreted as high level and 4.50 for married group, interpreted as very high level.

Table 8
Level of adversity of teachers in the area of emotional when grouped according to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...				
1. managing and controlling patience in teaching students	3.35	Moderate Level	3.19	Moderate Level
2. expressing concerns to my co-teachers and school head.	3.14	Moderate Level	3.17	Moderate Level
3. competitive and confrontational workplace.	3.07	Moderate Level	3.17	Moderate Level
4. having space to discuss my emotions and issues	3.14	Moderate Level	3.12	Moderate Level
5. managing conflicts between parents	3.07	Moderate Level	3.07	Moderate Level
6. managing the behavior of students	4.39	High Level	4.51	Very High Level
7. responding to bullying situation	3.03	Moderate Level	3.02	Moderate Level
Mean	3.31	Moderate Level	3.32	Moderate Level

Table 8 shows an overall mean score of 3.31 for the shorter length of service group and 3.32 for the longer length of service group, interpreted as moderate level. Item No.7, which states "responding in bullying situation," got the lowest mean score of 3.03 for the shorter length of service group, and for the longer length of service group 3.02, interpreted as a moderate level. On the other hand, Item No. 6, which states "managing behavior of students," got the highest mean score of 4.39 for the shorter length of service group, interpreted as high level, and 4.51 for the longer length of service group, interpreted as very high level.

Table 9

Level of adversity of teachers in the area of mental when grouped according to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...				
1. accomplishing reports and other paper works on time	4.96	Very High Level	4.97	Very High Level
2. looking for resources available to help struggling students.	3.06	Moderate Level	3.02	Moderate Level
3. learning ICT utilization in classes and personal use	4	High Level	4	High Level
4. hours spent on paperwork and insufficient time for vacation/leisure	4.06	High Level	3.94	High Level
5. seminars related to my ancillaries.	3.87	High Level	3.91	High Level
6. independently working with parents and other stakeholders to help resolve classroom/school issues.	3.96	High Level	4	High Level
7. the presence of excessive workload and hours of work	3.96	High Level	4.02	High Level
Mean	3.98	High Level	3.98	High Level

Table 9 shows an overall mean score of 3.98 for the younger group and 3.98 for the older group, which is interpreted as a high level. Item No. 2, which states "looking for resources available to help struggling students," got the lowest mean score of 3.06 for the younger group and 3.02 for the older group, interpreted as a moderate level. On the other hand, Item No. 1, which states "accomplishing reports and other paper works on time," got the highest mean score of 4.96 for the younger group and 4.97 for the older group, interpreted as a very high level.

Table 10

Level of adversity of teachers in the area of mental when grouped according to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...				
1. accomplishing reports and other paper works on time	4.95	Very High Level	4.97	Very High Level
2. looking for resources available to help struggling students.	3.04	Moderate Level	3.04	Moderate Level
3. learning ICT utilization in classes and	4	High Level	4	High Level

4.	personal use hours spent on paperwork and insufficient time for vacation/leisure	3.95	High Level	4.02	High Level
5.	seminars related to my ancillaries.	3.86	High Level	3.91	High Level
6.	independently working with parents and other stakeholders to help resolve classroom/school issues.	3.95	High Level	4	High Level
7.	the presence of excessive workload and hours of work	4	High Level	4	High Level
Mean		3.96	High Level	3.99	High Level

Table 10 shows an overall mean score of 3.96 for the male group and 3.99 for the female group, interpreted as high level. Item No. 2, which states "looking for resources available to help struggling students," got the lowest mean score of 3.04 for the male and 3.04 for the female groups, interpreted as a moderate level. On the other hand, Item No. 1, which states "accomplishing reports and other paper works on time," got the highest mean score of 4.95 for the male group and 4.97 for the female group, interpreted as very high level.

Table 11

Level of adversity of teachers in the area of mental when grouped according to Civil Status

Items	Single		Married		
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...					
1.	accomplishing reports and other paper works on time	4.94	Very High Level	4.98	Very High Level
2.	looking for resources available to help struggling students.	3.05	Moderate Level	3.04	Moderate Level
3.	learning ICT utilization in classes and personal use	4	High Level	4	High Level
4.	hours spent on paperwork and insufficient time for vacation/leisure	4	High Level	4	High Level
5.	seminars related to my ancillaries.	3.78	High Level	3.94	High Level
6.	independently working with parents and other stakeholders to help resolve classroom/school issues.	3.94	High Level	4	High Level
7.	the presence of excessive workload and hours of work	3.89	High Level	4.04	High Level
Mean		3.94	High Level	4.00	High Level

Table 11 shows an overall mean score of 3.96 for the single group and 4.00 for the married group, which is interpreted as a high level. Item No. 2, which states "looking for resources available to help struggling students," got the lowest mean score of 3.05 for the single group and 3.04 for the married group, interpreted as a moderate level. On the other hand, Item No. 1, which states "accomplishing reports and other paper works on time," got the highest mean score of 4.94 for the single group and 4.98 for the married group, interpreted as very high level.

Table 12

Level of adversity of teachers in the area of mental when grouped according to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer		
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...					
1.	accomplishing reports and other paper works on time	4.96	Very High Level	4.97	Very High Level
2.	looking for resources available to help struggling students.	3.07	Moderate Level	3.02	Moderate Level
3.	learning ICT utilization in classes and personal use	4	High Level	4	High Level
4.	hours spent on paperwork and insufficient time for vacation/leisure	4.03	High Level	3.97	High Level
5.	seminars related to my ancillaries.	3.92	High Level	3.87	High Level
6.	independently working with parents and other stakeholders to help resolve	3.92	High Level	4.02	High Level

	classroom/school issues.				
7.	the presence of excessive workload and hours of work	3.92	High Level	4.04	High Level
Mean		3.97	High Level	3.98	High Level

Table 12 shows an overall mean score of 3.97 for the shorter length of service group and 3.98 for the longer length of service group, which can be interpreted as high level. Item No. 2, which states "looking for resources available to help struggling students," got the lowest mean score of 3.07 for the shorter length of service group and 3.02 for the longer length of service group, interpreted as moderate level. On the other hand, item No. 1, which states "accomplishing reports and other paperwork on time," got the highest mean score of 4.96 for shorter lengths of service group and 4.97 for longer lengths of service group, interpreted as a very high level.

Table 13

Level of adversity of teachers in the area of finances when grouped according to Age

Items	Younger		Older		
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...					
1.	mounting teaching expenses in school	4.06	High Level	4	High Level
2.	providing for the needs of my children and family.	3.96	High Level	3.97	Moderate Level
3.	huge debts and shark loan companies.	4.06	High Level	3.94	High Level
4.	having a full command of my financial resources without hang-ups.	3.96	High Level	3.91	High Level
5.	creating opportunities for myself to have an extra income after school hours.	4.93	Very High Level	4.72	Very High Level
6.	managing ends meet from the last to the next salary day.	3.81	High Level	4.02	High Level
7.	saving a little extra from the remuneration I receive.	3.96	High Level	3.97	High Level
Mean		4.11	High Level	4.08	High Level

Table 13 shows an overall mean score of 4.11 for the younger group and 4.08 for the older group, which is interpreted as a high level. Item No. 6, which states "managing ends meet from the last to the next salary day," got the lowest mean score of 3.81 for the younger group, which can be interpreted as a high level. For older ones, item no. 4, which states, "having a full command of my financial resources without hang-ups," is their lowest, with a score of 3.91, interpreted as a high level. On the other hand, Item No. 5, which states "creating opportunities for myself to have an extra income after school hours," got the highest mean score of 4.93 for the younger group and 4.72 for the older group, interpreted as a very high level.

Table 14

Level of adversity of teachers in the area of finances when grouped according to Sex

Items	Male		Female		
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...					
1.	mounting teaching expenses in school	4	High Level	4.04	High Level
2.	providing for the needs of my children and family.	3.95	High Level	3.97	High Level
3.	huge debts and shark loan companies.	4.04	High Level	3.97	High Level
4.	having a full command of my financial resources without hang-ups.	3.95	High Level	3.93	High Level
5.	creating opportunities for myself to have an extra income after school hours.	4.91	Very High Level	4.78	Very High Level
6.	managing ends meet from the last to the next salary day.	4	High Level	3.89	High Level
7.	saving a little extra from the remuneration I receive.	3.91	High Level	4	High Level
Mean		4.11	High Level	4.08	High Level

Table 14 shows an overall mean score of 4.11 for the male group and 4.08 for the female group, which is interpreted as a high level. Item No. 7, which states, "saving a little extra from the remuneration I receive," got the lowest mean score of 3.91 for the female group, which can be interpreted as a high level. For older ones, item no. 6, which states, "managing ends meet from the last to the next salary day," is their lowest with a score of 3.89, interpreted as high level. On the other hand, Item No. 5 which states "creating opportunities for myself to have an extra income after school hours" got the highest mean score of 4.91 for the male group and 4.78 for female group, interpreted as a very high level.

Table 15

Level of adversity of teachers in the area of finances when grouped according to Civil Status

Items	Single Mean	Interpretation	Married Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...				
1. mounting teaching expenses in school	4.05	High Level	4.02	High Level
2. providing for the needs of my children and family.	3.94	High Level	3.98	High Level
3. huge debts and shark loan companies.	4	High Level	4	High Level
4. having a full command of my financial resources without hang-ups.	3.94	High Level	3.94	High Level
5. creating opportunities for myself to have an extra income after school hours.	4.89	Very High Level	4.8	Very High Level
6. managing ends meet from the last to the next salary day.	3.94	High Level	3.92	High Level
7. saving a little extra from the remuneration I receive.	3.94	High Level	3.98	High Level
Mean	4.10	High Level	4.09	High Level

Table 15 shows an overall mean score of 4.10 for the single group and 4.09 for the married group, which is interpreted as a high level. Item Nos. 2, 4, 6, and 7 which respectively state, "providing for the needs of my children and family", "having a full command of my financial resources without hang-ups", "managing ends meet from the last to the next salary day" and "saving a little extra from the remuneration I receive" got the lowest mean score of 3.94 for a single group, interpreted as high level. For married ones, item no. 6, which states, "managing ends meet from the last to the next salary day" is their lowest with a score of 3.92, interpreted as a high level. On the other hand, Item No. 5 which states "creating opportunities for myself to have an extra income after school hours" got the highest mean score of 4.89 for the single group and 4.80 for the married group, interpreted as very high level.

Table 16

Level of adversity of teachers in the area of finances when grouped according to Length of Service

Items	Shorter Mean	Interpretation	Longer Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I am challenged in ...				
1. mounting teaching expenses in school	3.96	High Level	4.07	High Level
2. providing for the needs of my children and family.	3.92	High Level	4	High Level
3. huge debts and shark loan companies.	4	High Level	4	High Level
4. having a complete command of my financial resources without hang-ups.	3.89	High Level	3.97	High Level
5. creating opportunities for myself to have an extra income after school hours.	4.89	Very High Level	4.78	Very High Level
6. managing ends meet from the last to the next salary day.	3.85	High Level	3.97	High Level
7. saving a little extra from the remuneration I receive.	4	High Level	3.95	High Level
Mean	4.07	High Level	4.10	High Level

Table 16 shows an overall mean score of 4.07 for the shorter length of service group and 4.09 for the longer length of service group, which is interpreted as a high level. Item Nos. 6, which states "managing ends meet

from the last to the next salary day," got the lowest mean score of 3.85 for the shorter length of the service group, which can be interpreted as a high level. For a longer-term service group, item 7 states, "saving a little extra from the remuneration I receive," which is their lowest, with a score of 3.95, interpreted as a high level. On the other hand, Item No. 5, which states "creating opportunities for myself to have an extra income after school hours," got the highest mean score of 4.89 for the shorter length of service group and 4.78 for the longer length of service group, interpreted as very high level.

Table 17
Difference in the level of adversity of teachers in the Area of emotional When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	32	35.70	569.50	0.780		Not Significant
	Older	37	34.39				
Sex	Male	23	29.57	404.00	0.100	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	46	37.72				
Civil Status	Single	19	34.66	468.50	0.928		Not Significant
	Married	50	35.13				
Length of Service	Shorter	28	33.86	542.00	0.686	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	41	35.78				

Table 17 result shows that when grouped and compared according to age, sex, civil status and length of service, a computed Mann-Whitney U test, which is higher than the 0.05 significance level, is interpreted as insignificant. Thus, the hypothesis that "there is no significant difference in the level of adversity of teachers when grouped and compared according to variables" was accepted.

Table 18
Difference in the level of adversity of teachers in the Area of mental When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	32	34.75	584.00	0.918		Not Significant
	Older	37	35.22				
Sex	Male	23	32.59	473.50	0.451	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	46	36.21				
Civil Status	Single	19	30.32	386.00	0.202		Not Significant
	Married	50	36.78				
Length of Service	Shorter	28	34.57	562.00	0.876	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	41	35.29				

Table 18 result shows that when grouped and compared according to age, sex, civil status, and length of service, a computed Mann-Whitney U test was obtained, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance and is interpreted as not significant. Thus, the hypothesis that "there is no significant difference in the level of adversity of teachers when grouped and compared according to variables" was accepted.

Table 19
Difference in the level of adversity of teachers in the Area of financial When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	32	35.36	580.50	0.881		Not Significant
	Older	37	34.69				
Sex	Male	23	36.09	504.00	0.732	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	46	34.46				
Civil Status	Single	19	34.84	472.00	0.965		Not Significant
	Married	50	35.06				
Length of Service	Shorter	28	34.09	548.50	0.737	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	41	35.62				

Table 19 result shows that when grouped and compared according to age, sex, civil status, and length of service, a computed Mann-Whitney U test was obtained, which is higher than the 0.05 significance level and is interpreted as insignificant. Thus, the hypothesis that "there is no significant difference in the level of adversity of teachers when grouped and compared according to variables" was accepted.

Table 20

Relationship between the level of teachers' adversity and learners' performance

Variables	Rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Teachers' Adversity	-0.070	0.566	0.05	Not Significant
Learners' Performance				

The table 20 result shows that the level of teachers' adversity and learners' performance obtained a computed rho-value of -0.070 and p-value of 0.566, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as not significant.

Conclusion

From the foregoing results of the study, the following conclusions are drawn: Teachers are experiencing challenges, particularly in the mental and financial aspects. Learners were performing well as they achieved outstanding results. Even though many factors could affect students' performance, they can still perform well. The difference in the areas of emotional, mental, and financial in the level of adversity of teachers was insignificant. The level of teachers' adversity does not have significant relationship on the level of learners' performance.

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